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BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

D7.2: Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M12

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Executive Summary

BIOFIN-EU seeks to create a unifying framework and technology that creates the enabling conditions for nature-positive investments. Activities that protect and restore biodiversity (such as Nature-based Solutions (NbS)) are frequently unique and mainly carried out via multi-actor efforts at a local scale with positive, but complex outcomes. BIOFIN-EU use a multi-actor approach to create impact through a science-led Dashboard which helps actors navigate large-scale financing challenges and to develop, replicate, scale out and strengthen NbS-investment, creating a more sustainable, vibrant, resilient and healthy planet and supporting the EU's biodiversity restoration ambitions. BIOFIN-EU will also produce several key exploitable results (KERS) that will offer extensive positive impact including:

- **NbS Database**
- **Nature-Positive Business Model Builder**
- **Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine**
- **Skills and Knowledge Accelerators**

The BIOFIN-EU Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (DEC) plan provides guidelines for successfully sharing the impacts and benefits of the project with society, transferring knowledge, describing results so they are available for use/re-use and defining concrete actions for that use/re-use.

The aim of this document is to present a clear and coherent dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy which serves as a cornerstone for all the outreach activities envisaged to be carried out throughout the project thus, ensuring broad communication throughout the project's course. Progress monitoring throughout the project's duration is also a part of the process.

The deliverable aims to:

- organise the communication flow of the information that is shared with the project stakeholders and key actors of the NbS/financial community (external environment), as well as the information shared within the BIOFIN-EU consortium (internal environment);
- maintain the project's brand and unique identity to facilitate the delivery of messages which capture and sustain the target groups' attention constantly and in a comprehensive and gripping manner;
- encourage the audience to act by determining the actions that can have a positive impact on the project and its objectives

This document is the second version of the DEC plan which will be updated to monitor the plan's implementation on M24 & M36 including project advancements and any outcomes from the learning sites. The information will be updated with contributions from all BIOFIN-EU partners, from the monitoring of the progress of the communication and dissemination activities, as well as the exploitation pathways for the project's key results. The deliverable will be finalised by concluding all the dissemination and communication results, their achievement and impact as well as planning for relevant activities after the project ends.

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
BECC	Behaviour Energy and Climate Change
D	Deliverable
EO	Expected Outcome
ES	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IASB	International Accounting Standards Board
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LS	Learning Sites
M	Month
NbS	Nature Based Solutions
NFCs	Non-Financial Corporations
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
RIA	Research and Innovation
SFT	Sustainable Finance Taxonomy
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

Challenge

Nature is essential for human existence and our quality of life and society is directly and indirectly dependent on the natural environment, its biodiversity and ecosystem services. We now know that the design of the globalised financial system, which seeks to optimise financial return irrespective of its secondary impacts, is contributing to large-scale biodiversity loss and bringing our biosphere closer to collapse. Yet our modern economics lives are directed by financial institutions and markets. They influence the products we consume (via corporate financing choices), where and how we live (via lending and insurance products), access to energy, food and transport services (via corporate and public enterprise investment) and where we place our savings (via asset management). Behind this front door, the financial system is formed from networks of financial institutions and intermediaries deploying decision-making tools and instruments that direct and redirect the flow of capital. The EU Green Deal and the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy (SFT) provide an important starting point for placing a bound on the destructive power of capital and redirecting financial flows towards nature-positive economic activity.

Aim and approach

BIOFIN-EU's initiative encompasses the development of a pioneering unifying framework and technology designed to create the enabling conditions for large-scale nature-positive investments. Recognizing the complexity of activities that protect and restore biodiversity, such as nature-based solutions (NbS), BIOFIN-EU will establish a categorization of NbS, a menu of effective governance structures, and a comprehensive library of stakeholder engagement strategies. This strategic move will draw on expertise and best practices in natural capital and economics to streamline decision-making, accelerate transaction completion, and standardise the investment process.

BIOFIN-EU's core ambition is to overcome existing boundaries by deploying a science-led cutting-edge data-driven analytics dashboard for nature-positive financial decision support. An underwriting engine will advance project appraisal, risk assessment, and outcome modelling, ushering in a twin green and digital transition to resolve transaction complexity and support the EU in achieving its biodiversity goals.

Consortium

The BIOFIN-EU consortium consists of **13 partners** coming from **10 different countries**. Together all partners form a complete group uniting the necessary expertise, skills, interdisciplinary knowledge and resources capable of achieving the demanding projects goals.

1.2. Document scope and structure

The present Deliverable 7.2 - Dissemination, exploitation communication (DEC) plan (2nd version) is developed within the framework of WP7 Impact Maximization. The aim of the deliverable is to integrate the overall dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy of BIOFIN-EU, from day one, to define the goals of DEC activities, identify the most efficient means to achieve them, and decompose them into a detailed implementation plan. To this end, the DEC plan sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited in order to effectively spread BIOFIN-EU activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences. Additionally, the BIOFIN-EU DEC plan, aims to set the pace and a number of foreseen activities in order to place the cornerstone for the successful commercialisation and market uptake of BIOFIN-EU solutions.

This document (D7.2) continues to act as a reference point to all BIOFIN's partners when carrying out DEC activities related to the project. Delivered in M12, D7.2 will be updated at M24 (version 3) and M36 (version 4), presenting progress on reaching Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as described within.

The document is outlined in **6** chapters, structured to appropriately present the overall BIOFIN-EU DEC objectives, strategy, target audiences, tools and means, channels and material for an efficient and effective implementation of dissemination, communication and exploitation activities within the project lifespan.

This document is comprised of the following 6 chapters:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project, the document scope and its overall structure.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project's DEC methodology and approach including target groups and key messages and specifies the reporting and monitoring procedures and tools.

Chapter 3 describes BIOFIN-EU's dissemination measures and activities and partner's dissemination KPIs.

Chapter 4 describes BIOFIN-EU's communication measures and activities and partner's communication KPIs.

Chapter 5 references version 1 of the DEC Plan (D7.1) from M3 and D7.5 Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1 (M12) for the BIOFIN-EU's exploitation strategy and project KERs.

Chapter 6 presents the overall conclusions.

Annex I presents an overview of the D&C reporting tool.

Annex II presents the full BIOFIN-EU Brand Book.

Annex III presents the full BIOFIN-EU deliverable template.

2. DEC Methodology and Approach

A strong DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and provides a concrete roadmap for partners in order to boost the growth of the BIOFIN-EU ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities and maximise impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level. BIOFIN-EU sets clear Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination measures to promote visibility of the project hence more benefits. The plan follows a targeted multi-actor and multichannel approach with objectives and measures chosen to maximise information dispersal about the project and its results to all identified target groups. It is intertwined with a sound exploitation strategy (D7.5 Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1), ensuring lasting stakeholder engagement and exploitation of the NbS Dashboard components and project results.

During the lifespan of the BIOFIN-EU project a tailored multi-channel and multi-dimensional plan for dissemination and exploitation of results including Communication measures (DEC plan) unfolds, taking into account GDPR (D1.2 Data Management Plan M6, M18, M36) and Gender equality issues (social and ethical).

In the context of BIOFIN-EU's overall Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan, specific KPIs have been established to promote awareness and engagement with target audiences.

The initial allocation of KPIs—defined per reporting period and per partner—serves as a **preliminary framework** aimed at fostering accountability, facilitating target achievement, and ensuring an effective distribution of goals over time. While this allocation provides structure at the project's outset, it is **non-binding** and may **be adjusted** in response to the project's evolving needs. Any modifications to the KPI allocation, whether by reporting period or by partner, will be transparently **documented in the DEC Plan**, with a clear **rationale provided**. All parties involved in the project will be promptly informed of such updates to ensure alignment across the consortium.

2.1. DEC Methodology

The BIOFIN-EU DEC plan is based on the **SOSTAC** model approach¹ which will be considered in every phase of the Dissemination and Communication activities. The SOSTAC model includes the following key elements:

Situation analysis: A state-of-play analysis which identifies and explains the current challenges to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal, and economic impacts during and after the project and the potential IPR of the results. A preliminary situation analysis is at the foundation of the DEC plan.

Objectives: The DEC plan will elaborate upon clear and measurable objectives (Section 2.4) that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination, and exploitation measures.

Strategy: Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication (Section 2.3).

¹ SOSTAC® Guide to your Perfect Digital Marketing Plan (2022) (Editor P R Smith) 7th Edition (<https://prsmith.org/books>)

Figure 1: SOSTAC Methodology

Tactics: Identification of the traditional and digital communication tools and various dissemination activities that will allow the consortium to implement its strategy (Chapters 3 & 4).

Actions: The DEC plan will build upon the activities, tools and channels defined in the proposal and include the contributions expected from partners, and their distribution over the duration of the project. Preliminary exploitation pathways will be addressed (Chapter 5) and Open Science practices will be factored into all aspects of DEC implementation (Section 3.2.1).

Control: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets determined during the proposal will be used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting will also be used along with digital tools for record keeping, all of which will be presented in Section 2.6.

2.2. BIOFIN-EU DEC Time plan

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 2) is crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the achievement of the objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan (Phase 1: Vision, Phase 2: Raise cognition, Phase 3: Multiplier effect, Phase 4: Sustainability) last from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability. Each phase has an overarching objective that will provide focus to activities and create a steady workflow attuned to the work done and results produced by other WPs.

Figure 2: BIOFIN-EU DEC Implementation Time Plan

These measures aim both to highlight the ongoing use and reuse of the project's results and ensure lasting interest and engagement with the project's broader objectives. They will be expanded upon and further developed in the final iteration of the DEC plan. In addition, a multifaceted sustainability plan with tools to

maintain and strengthen the ecosystem, ongoing collaborations and support the forward trajectory of BIOFIN-EU products and solutions will be created as part of the deliverables D7.5-D7.7.

2.3. Target groups and key messages

Six target groups have been identified to categorically define all parties that could have an interest in the project and its results. To summarise the benefit to each group, key messages have been created tailored to target audience's specificities and matching their level of interest (Table 1). General breakdown of activities and channels meant to engage each group has been defined (Table 2). Table 2 will be updated accordingly, if needed, on the third version of the DEC Plan (D7.3) at M24, based on the project's results.

Table 1: Target groups and their key messages

	TG1: Professional Ecosystem
	Members: Auditing firms, Professional education organisations, NFC representative group
Key message: <i>Understand and employ BIOFIN's innovations on Ecosystem restoration/protection and receive training on how to acknowledge and assess the use of NbS</i>	
	TG2: Financial Actors
	Members: Pension and investment managers, private equity firms, venture capital firms, banking and insurance institutions (retail, trust banks), Entrepreneurial Finance.
Key message: <i>Exploit data driven innovations and improved data access to maximise performance, efficiency and stable profit increase</i>	
	TG3: NbS Providers
	Members: 'Internal' NbS (in Non-Financial Corporation, NFCs) and 'External' NbS providers (landowners, farmers, etc)
Key message: <i>Empower decision-making towards NbS with minimum risk and cost transactions</i>	
	TG4: Policy makers & Standardization Bodies
	Members: Public authorities and standardisation organisations (FSC, etc)
Key message: <i>Implement NbS centred policies based on evidence and LS data and monitor / evaluate the sustainability and impact of those policy measures for successful implementation of SFT</i>	
	TG5: Research Organisations
	Members: Universities, students, faculties, and research institutes
Key message: <i>Contribute to cutting edge research in NbS and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects</i>	

	TG6: General Public
	Members: Citizens and their associations, NGOs
Key message: <i>Gain insights on addressing climate challenges associated with biodiversity loss</i>	

Specific communication tools and channels have been scheduled to reach the identified target groups:

Table 2: Communication tools and channels for target audience Channels, tools, and activities

Target Groups						
Communication tools & channels	TG1: Professional Ecosystem	TG2: Financial Actors	TG3: NbS Providers	TG4: Policy makers & Standardization Bodies	TG5: Research Organisations	TG6: General Public
Branding & material	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ focus on the society
Social media platforms	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ focus on the society
e-Newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multimedia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multiplier campaigns	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Scientific Publications	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Technical articles	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Ecosystem Building	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Capacity Building	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Standards & Policy Contribution				✓	✓	

2.4. DEC Objectives and KPIs

BIOFIN-EU will provide a mechanism for a more holistic approach to capital allocation and the mobilisation of mainstream finance towards impactful nature-positive (see Figure 3) by delivering three key tools (*BIOFIN Database*, *BIOFIN Nature-Positive Business Model Builder*, *BIOFIN Data Analytics & Underwriting Engine*) embedded within the NbS Dashboard that will enable impacts to deliver the outcomes specified in

the call (detailed below). BIOFIN-EU will also identify policy recommendations that address remaining implementation gaps about how mainstream finance can be redirected to protecting and restoring biodiversity to support the goals of EU Green Deals action plans and EUs biodiversity strategy for 2030. There are an estimated 2 million people employed in the banking sector alone in Europe. The required change in knowledge, skills and processes is enormous and BIOFIN-EU's portfolio of training, business simulation and case studies (*Skills and Knowledge Accelerators*) will be co-designed with target groups: financial institutions, NFCs; policy makers; researchers; and citizens, to be accessible, flexible and durable. The open access NbS Dashboard will endure beyond the proposed Innovation Action, to 2030. These tools will be used by BIOFIN-EU partners and BIOFIN-EU's six target groups facilitated and amplified through project partners SUL, IOB and ILSI.

Figure 3: BIOFIN-EU's contribution towards the Expected Outcome specified in this topic

Dissemination Objectives

The main objective behind the dissemination strategy is to maximise the impact of the project, to increase its visibility, and to ensure that project outputs reach a wide audience of relevant stakeholders.

The plan follows a targeted multi-actor and multi-channel approach with objectives and measures chosen to maximise information dispersal about the project and its results to all identified target groups. It is intertwined with a sound exploitation strategy (D7.5 Integrated toolset for Multiplying Impact v1), ensuring lasting stakeholder engagement and exploitation of the NbS Dashboard components and project results.

BIOFIN-EU applies an intensive dissemination strategy that leads all relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy is aligned with the dissemination objectives as described below:

- Maximise results' impact
- Facilitate other researchers to advance their research
- Contribute to the advancement of the State of the Art
- Make scientific results a common good

Figure 4: BIOFIN-EU Dissemination KPIs

Communication Objectives

BIOFIN-EU's communication strategy combines a wide but also targeted mechanism for communication actions. Project partners strategically carry out communication activities through both physical and digital means. RAINNO creates and conveys clear tailored and diverse key messages, raise awareness of project activities, enable active engagement, provide efficient dissemination and overall, maximise impact among key stakeholders and target groups at a broader social, policy, and industry level.

BIOFIN-EU's communication strategy has been designed and executed, with main focus on informing, promoting and passing all the project's activities to a spectrum of audiences such as citizens, media, investors and relevant stakeholders. Programmed to take place from the start of the project and to ensure that the communication measures will effectively address the project's expectations, communication objectives have been set to:

- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability-oriented technology innovations;
- Encourage positive reception and acceptance by financial actors, policy makers & standardisation bodies;
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools, and channels;
- Raise awareness on how public money is spent;
- Show the success of European collaboration;
- Generate market demand.

Figure 5: BIOFIN-EU Communication KPIs

Exploitation Objectives

The exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, BIOFIN-EU's exploitation activities are recognized as the key enabler for success of the project. All the consortium partners are committed to the exploitation of the project's results and their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring BIOFIN-EU's results to all targeted stakeholders. A combination of activities spans throughout the project duration and vary in intensity, based on the amount of information that can be made available and the results that will be produced during the project's lifetime. The objectives of the project's exploitation measures include:

- Secure positive engagement from relevant stakeholders since it is important to attain both their contributions to the process as well as their willingness to use the results;
- Enhance and facilitate the exploitation of the project's results both by the consortium partners and the stakeholders.

BIOFIN-EU aims to capture the added value of project results, which will be valorised by:

- Creating feasible paths to deliver project's results to stakeholders interested in their use/reuse;
- Elaborating upon and defining new Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to expedite development and commercialisation when possible.

2.5. Multi-actor approach methodology

The multi-actor approach promotes collaborative, participatory, and solution-oriented approaches to address complex societal challenges and drive positive change. The 'multi-actor' approach is key to the interactive innovation model. Interactive innovation "stresses relations between actors and process"² where the most important resources are the diverse types of knowledge and their links, and interactive learning is the most valuable process. In this context, the multi-actor approach and the way diverse actors

² Johannessen, J. A. (2009). A Systemic Approach to Innovation: The Interactive Innovation Model. *Kybernetes*, 38, 158-176. <https://doi.org/10.1108/0368492091093033>

work well together is central to effectively delivering unique, impactful results. **BIOFIN-EU uses a multi-actor approach**, bringing together all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to appraise, gather, cocreate and disseminate practical solutions to real needs and achieve the project's aims. **Interactive innovation requires a participatory 'bottom-up approach,'** facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. This is a social process rather than a 'top-down' scientific approach and also allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation.

Multi-actor interactive innovation brings all the competent actors with various knowledge together, with the aim to plan and codesign practical and implementable solutions to real-life problems. BIOFIN-EU has embodied the multi-actor approach from the inception of the project, following by:

- Targeting real-life needs, challenging current problems, and looking for relevant opportunities.
- Bringing together a consortium with diverse yet complementary knowledge and skills.
- Integrating opportunities to include end users across work packages. BIOFIN's multi-actor co-design methodology will be used to generate tools for the NBS Dashboard (WP2-5) and contribute to policy recommendations (WP6) relating to the SFT.

During the implementation stage, the multi actor approach is fundamental to the project's overall strategy:

- Work packages have clearly defined the roles of partners, and in the context of the DEC plan, clear KPIs and expectations have been established.
- Knowledge exchange activities beyond consortium meetings will be organised at the discretion of task leaders with the support of RAINNO as DEC manager.
- The project management guidelines will ensure opportunities exist for co-creation and co-decision making with partners.

It also extends to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the end user;
- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate;
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry, society and government;
- Capitalising on partners existing connections, networks and events program;
- Including knowledge exchange activities and discussion in event programs.

Key Scenarios

Based upon the *LIAISON project Practitioner Handbook*³, a series of specific scenarios and tools have been identified to ensure interactive innovation and the multi-actor approach are utilised during the project implementation. The handbook also serves as a reference and additional tools may be utilised.

³ LIAISON (2021) Practitioner Handbook: Evaluation and Impact Assessment of Interactive Innovation. <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

Figure 6: BIOFIN-EU multi-actor approach key scenarios

Specific tools have also been selected to achieve the goals of each scenario and have also considered the timing of implementation, the size of the group, resource required and level of technical difficulty.

Scenario 1: ENGAGE

Tool: INTEREST- INFLUENCE MATRIX

This tool helps identify crucial actors that both positively shape the network and those that could negatively influence the network. This helps clearly understand the stakeholders that are the most important for interactive innovation. The tool can be used at multiple times, but the analysis should only be conducted at a given time and repeated to compare results. Figure 7 represents the matrix provided by the LIASON practitioner handbook. The four categories are formed from the relationship between interest of stakeholders and their influence. A best-case scenario is when there is both high interest and influence.

Figure 7: Stakeholder influence, interest matrix

This tool will be used iteratively throughout the project implementation to access and improve networks and collaborations and will particularly be useful for the participatory workshops.

Scenario 2: EXAMINE

Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING

The tool is used to understand the experiences and knowledge of the stakeholders within the project, identifying impacts of the project and their subjective evaluations of the project. The tool intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder's experiences match with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences.

The journey mapping tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 3: CREATE

Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

The tool is used for assessing cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, which should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised.

The tool has been used during the project development stage, but it can be used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.

Scenario 4: ADDRESS

Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process and helping them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation.

TRIZ tool can be used throughout the project implementation whenever new knowledge is required from the outside.

Scenario 5: PLAN

Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and How?

It will ensure that the time of partners and stakeholders is well used and will minimise stakeholder fatigue and duplication of tasks.

This tool will be used throughout the implementation of the project.

Scenario 6: EVALUATE

Tool: 'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

The tool will help internalise new forms of knowledge and ideas that have been created through brainstorming. The aim will be to help generate hypotheses regarding the cause of effects of actions leading to actions then to results. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans.

The tool will be used throughout the project implementation.

2.6. Planning and reporting procedures

Two main actions for all partners have been designed in order to plan and report all of their activities:

A. Planning

Partners are asked to provide a plan for their dissemination and communication activities each semester through a dedicated spreadsheet with three tables:

1. BIOFIN-EU Event Planning

Events that are already in the partners organisation's calendar with relevant local, regional and/or national events.

2. BIOFIN-EU Synergy Mapping

Projects that partners are currently involved in. Working groups, networks, alliances that consortium partners are involved in. Other potential synergy opportunities could be foreseen.

3. BIOFIN-EU Publication Planning

Peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, magazine articles and any other publication partners have planned.

1. BIOFIN-EU Event Planning						
Please complete the following form with events that you are already planning on attending over the next 6 months, or any that you are aware of and feel would be well suited for BIOFIN-EU participation.						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link (if applicable)	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential BIOFIN-EU involvement
	e.g. Conference, Seminar, Webinar, Workshop, Exhibition, etc.		DD/MM/YY / City, Country	e.g. Local, Regional, National, European, International level	The target groups that will attend the event (e.g. Professional Ecosystem, Financial Actors, NBS Providers, Policy makers & Standardization Bodies, Research Organisations, General Public)	e.g. Presentation, Booth, Workshop, Banner ect.
2. BIOFIN-EU Synergy & Liaison mapping						
Please complete the following form with projects, initiatives and/or networks that you are involved with or are aware of and that could provide an opportunity for joint activities and collaboration.						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities
	e.g. Project, Living Lab, Initiative, Working Group	The full name of the initiative		The initiative's main contact or person responsible for the initiative. (e.g. coordinator, project manager) Name and email address.	Provide a brief description of the initiative's focus area or main activity or aim e.g. climate change/mitigation measures and future risks	e.g. Participation in common events, Joint publications, Sharing events on websites ect.
3. BIOFIN-EU Publication Planning						
Please complete the following table with journals, magazines etc. that you intend to publish any progress/results/details of the BIOFIN-EU						
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date			
	e.g. Scientific, Technical publication/article, Magazine article, Best practice publication, White/Discussion Paper, Policy/Standards recommendations	Link to the potential journal, magazine, site of publication				

Figure 8: Spreadsheet for planning future events

The spreadsheet (Figure 8) has been uploaded by RAINNO to the project's common folder providing direct and continuous access to partners for updating reasons. Additionally, RAINNO sends monthly reminders to partners to update the forms with relevant information.

B. Reporting

Each month, all partners are requested to update an online inventory of any communication or dissemination activities and deposit corresponding promoting material such as photos, reports, etc. in a designated folder. This procedure reinforces accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process. The results are compiled and serve to monitor targets and inform DEC strategies

as the project progresses. RAINNO is responsible for monitoring the KPIs on a monthly basis and providing updates to the rest of the partners at relevant meetings. In case significant, or repeated deviations are recorded from certain partners, the coordinator will be officially informed. Deviations will have to be justified, discussed among partners, and changes in the DEC strategy will be reported on the updated versions of the DEC plan.

An online spreadsheet has been developed (**Annex I**) and uploaded on the projects SharePoint (<https://ulcampus.sharepoint.com/sites/ULBioFIN-EU>) and is available to all partners. This reporting form is designed for the easy input of dissemination and communication activities and helps maintain accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process.

The spreadsheet includes:

- **Sheet: Instructions** provides instructions on how to use the workbook and important notes regarding the dissemination & communication activities.
- **Sheet 1A: KPI targets per reporting period** and a short description of each KPI.
- **Sheet 2A: the total KPI targets per partner.**
- **Sheet 3A: Monitoring** of the KPI status (overall status, per reporting period and per partner).
- **Sheets 1-13 are dedicated to each partner**, containing one table for reporting the dissemination & communication activities and one table with the overall target for each KPI per partner.

Thus, all partners are able to provide a detailed report of their monthly D&C activities, including all the relevant information, such as the place, date and type of an event that have participated or organised, relevant photos, the type and number of stakeholders reached, and a drop-down list with all the KPIs, to link each activity with the appropriate KPI category.

3. Dissemination Activities

3.1. Dissemination KPIs

The main objective of the BIOFIN-EU dissemination strategy is to ensure the project's outcomes, knowledge and opportunities are effectively diffused to the appropriate target communities, making results widely accessible.

More specifically, the dissemination strategy's objectives are to:

- **Introduce** the NbS Dashboard and increase visibility among key stakeholders.
- **Capitalise** upon the Learning Sites and raise awareness on the NbS.
- **Promote** synergies with other research, policy and communication initiatives, taking advantage of existing dissemination networks and channels.
- **Engage** targeted audiences to get feedback, validate and ensure broad applicability, replication and scalability of the project's results.
- **Align** and integrate dissemination, communication, ecosystem building activities with exploitation and business modelling processes to allow scale up of outputs.
- **Support** continual exploitation of project results in research, public policy and other relevant driven initiatives.

All partners share the responsibility of communicating the project and disseminating the results. Depending on each partner's expertise, experience, and resource allocation, KPIs and targets were allocated (Table 3).

D7.2: Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan

Table 3: Dissemination KPIs per partner

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	1- UL	2- NAT	3- UGOT	4- UM	5- RAIN	6- SERDA	7- UNIPD	8- ETI	9- IOB	10- SUL	11- ILSI	12- QUB	13- COFAC
D.1	Scientific Publications														
D.1.1	Publications in Peer-reviewed journals	12	4	3	2	3									
D.1.2	Publications in scientific conferences	16	3	3	3	3			1		1			2	
D.1.3	Participation in scientific conferences	20	5	3	4	4			1		1			2	
D.2	Technical Articles														
D.2.1	Technical publications/Articles	20	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	1		3
D.2.2	White papers	6	2	1		1								2	
D.2.3	Discussion papers	6	1		1				1					2	1
D.2.4	Best practice publications	6	1	1	1	1								2	
D.2.5	Sectoral data & prediction reports	6	1					1	2	1					1
D.3	Ecosystem Building														
D.3.1	Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	3	1									1	1		
D.3.2	Participation in conferences	6	2		1	1					1	1			
D.3.3	Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	6	4				2								
D.3.4	Advisory board meetings	2	2												
D.3.5	Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	4	1	1										2	
D.3.6	Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	10	2		1		1	1		1	1	2		1	
D.3.7	Open days for academic and commercial awareness	10										10			
D.4	Capacity Building														
D.4.1	Co-Creation Workshops in 6 different countries	20	5	2		1		1	1	1	3			5	1
D.4.2	Online Training Tutorials	15									5	5	5		
D.4.3	Webinars	8	1				1				2	2	2		
D.5	Standards & Policy Contribution														
D.5.1	Reports from the BIOFIN Policy and Implementation Forum	3												3	
D.5.2	Recommendations on accounting standards development	3	2											1	

Dissemination KPIs have been distributed between **two reporting periods** (M1-M18, M19-M36) during in which the DEC plan will be updated in 4 versions. This is the **second version**, updated with the achieved dissemination KPIs up to **M12**, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Dissemination KPIs per reporting period and M12 status

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	Reporting Phases		
			M1-M18	M19-M36	M12 status
D.1	Scientific Publications				
D.1.1	Publications in Peer-reviewed journals	12	2	10	0/2
D.1.2	Publications in scientific conferences	16	4	12	0/4
D.1.3	Participation in scientific conferences	20	5	15	2/5
D.2	Technical Articles				
D.2.1	Technical publications/Articles	20	5	15	2/5
D.2.2	White papers	6	-	6	-
D.2.3	Discussion papers	6	-	6	-
D.2.4	Best practice publications	6	1	5	0/1
D.2.5	Sectoral data & prediction reports	6	-	6	-
D.3	Ecosystem Building				
D.3.1	Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows	3	1	2	0/1
D.3.2	Participation in conferences	6	1	5	2/1
D.3.3	Joint events with relevant EU funded projects and initiatives	6	2	4	0/2
D.3.4	Advisory board meetings	2	1	1	0/1
D.3.5	Scientific / data science workshops and/or webinars	4	1	3	1/1
D.3.6	Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars	10	4	6	4/4
D.3.7	Open days for academic and commercial awareness	10	0	10	-
D.4	Capacity Building				
D.4.1	Co-Creation Workshops in 6 different countries	20	8	12	0/8
D.4.3	Online Training Tutorials	15	3	12	0/3
D.4.4	Capacity Building Webinars	8	3	5	0/3
D.5	Standards & Policy Contribution				
D.5.1	Reports from the BIOFIN <i>Policy and Implementation Forum</i>	3	-	3	-
D.5.2	Recommendations on accounting standards development	3	-	3	-

The reporting mechanism (described in Section 2.6) will help maintain accountability and achieve these targets. The first reporting period of the project (M1-M18), regarding both the dissemination and communication (Section 4.1) activities, is fundamental for establishing connections and building interest around the project and will be used to:

- Map stakeholders and their needs that must be addressed;
- Develop the project's website, visual identity, communication materials and social media channels;
- Establish and implement the protocol for deciding publications and identifying synergies;
- Begin outreach to other projects, initiatives;
- Participate in events and publish press-releases and newsletters;
- Familiarise partners with all communications channels, templates, and protocols.

3.2. Dissemination Measures and Tools

3.2.1. Scientific publications

BIOFIN-EU foresees developing several scientific publications and participating in different scientific conferences, with the purpose of disseminating the research done under the project. All publications will

implement Open Access and Open peer-review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science.

Open Access

All publications will be published in open-access journals (green or gold). A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access ensure:

- Far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports;
- Greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community;
- Higher likelihood that future research and analysis facilitates building on and reuse BIOFIN-EU's results thereby helping in terms of reproducibility and continuity of the research results.

Procedures

With regards to publications, partners are requested to fill in the Publication Planning Template, which is part of the event planning spreadsheet (Figure 8), so there is tracking of what will be published and when. Moreover, with regards to publications (and presentations), during the project and for a period 1 year after the end of the project all partners are obliged to comply with the rules specified in the Grant Agreement. This includes:

- Prior notice of any planned publication should be given to the other parties at least forty-five calendar days before the publication.
- Any objection to the planned publication should include a precise request for necessary modifications and be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the coordinator and to the party or parties proposing the dissemination within thirty calendar days after receipt of the notice.
- If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, publication is permitted.

An objection is justified, and measures will be taken to overcome the objection if:

- The protection of the objecting party's results or background would be negatively affected, or
- The objecting party's legitimate interests in relation to its results or background would be significantly harmed, or
- The proposed publication includes confidential information of the objecting party.

In addition, the unpublished results or background of any partner will not be used for dissemination purposes without obtaining the owning party's prior written approval.

3.2.1.1. Publications in Peer-reviewed journals

BIOFIN-EU aims to publish at least **12 peer-reviewed journals** in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project's work. This task has been undertaken mostly by the university and research partners (UL, NAT, UGOT, UM) and publications cover several fields of the work performed within the BIOFIN-EU project. The BIOFIN-EU consortium has not yet published any peer-review scientific paper due to the early stage of the project. However, the plan is to publish 2 papers by the end of the first reporting period (M18).

3.2.1.2. Publications in scientific conferences

Research partners (UL, NAT, UGOT, UM, UNIPD, IOB, QUB) will also strive to publish **16 conference papers** in different relevant academic conferences. Those publications will help again in disseminating the project's results to the research community. BIOFIN-EU partners target to publish in 4 scientific conferences by the end of the first reporting period (M18).

3.2.1.3. Participation in scientific conferences

BIOFIN-EU partners will also participate in at least **20 scientific conferences** with the purpose of networking, staying in touch with the latest research relevant to the project and seeking strategic collaborations. The partners that will undertake this KPI are UL, NAT, UGOT, UM, UNIPD, IOB, and QUB. BIOFIN-EU partners target to participate in 5 scientific conferences by M18. Up to the date of this deliverable, partners have participated in **2** conferences. Table 5 below summarises the participation of BIOFIN-EU partners in scientific conferences. All future publications will also be included in Table 5 in the next iteration of the deliverable (M24).

Table 5: BIOFIN-EU participation in scientific conferences

Participation in scientific Conferences					
#	Date	Conference	Place	Partner	Target audience
1	18/06/2024	3rd World Biodiversity Forum 2024	Davos, Switzerland	UM	Industry, business partners; Research communities; Civil Society; Others
2	01/07/2024	33rd European Conference on Operational Research (EURO)	Copenhagen, Denmark	COFAC	Research communities; Others

On June 18, 2024, **UM** participated in the [3rd World Biodiversity Forum](#). The World Biodiversity Forum 2024, held from 16 to 20 June 2024 in Davos, Switzerland, gathered more than 800 leading researchers, practitioners, entrepreneurs, artists, and policymakers from 75 countries. It was organised by bioDISCOVERY, a Global Research Network (GRN) of FutureEarth, and the University of Zurich and its Research Priority Programme on "Global Change and Biodiversity". The aim of the World Biodiversity Forum is to advance biodiversity research in an integrative, interdisciplinary, and transparent fashion, and to further transdisciplinary approaches in biodiversity. The forum supports and aims to accelerate transformative approaches, ranging from fundamental research to implementation, by facilitating interactions between all stakeholders relevant to biodiversity, and by integrating multiple knowledge systems. During the conference, Christopher Brewster (UM) presented the BIOFIN-EU project and the initial work on developing a risk analysis underwriting engine for evaluating the risk and return on a specific investment (Figure 9).

An initial simplistic perspective

Figure 9: Presentation of BIOFIN-EU project during the 3rd World Biodiversity Forum by UM

On the 1st of July 2024, **COFAC** participated in the [33rd European Conference on Operational Research \(EURO\)](#) in Copenhagen, Denmark. EURO 2024 (CPH) is one of the largest European conferences on operations research and also the largest European networking event for optimization experts. Academics and practitioners from all over the world attended the conference and shared their latest findings. Around 3000 stakeholders from research community and other variety backgrounds attended the event, and 150 of them attended Francisco’s Silva Pinto (COFAC) session. In the framework of BIOFIN-EU, and more specifically the Learning Site in São Paulo, Brazil, he presented the emerging need to prioritise Nature-Based Solutions (Nbs) for sustainable water management (Figure 10).

Figure 10: COFAC presentation during the 33rd European Conference on Operational Research

3.2.2. Technical Articles

3.2.2.1. Technical publications/articles

Besides the creation of scientific publications, BIOFIN-EU will publish at least **20 technical publications/articles** in high quality technical blogs, magazines, catalogues, books or any other reference from technology providers (bottom-up) as well as references related to the application scenarios domains under consideration (top-down) with the aim to make the project and its results known to industrial stakeholders. During the first 12 months of the project **2** technical articles were published online as shown in the Table 6 below. For the first reporting period of the project, 5 technical publications/articles are anticipated to be published. All future publications will also be included in Table 6 in the next iteration of the deliverable (M24).

Table 6: BIOFIN-EU's Technical publications/articles

Technical Articles				
#	Date	Title	Partner	Website
1	28/06/2024	A inclusão de análise multicritério e otimização de portfólios para alavancar o financiamento privado de soluções com base na natureza (in English: Multi-criteria decision analysis and portfolio optimization to leverage private financing for nature-based solutions)	COFAC	http://apdio.pt/documents/10180/16684/Boletim70.pdf
2	16/12/2024	A Framework to Support the Financing of Ireland's Nature, Climate and Water Objectives by 2030	UL	Zenodo

3.2.2.2. White Papers and Discussion Papers

To achieve high-scale and long-lasting impact, BIOFIN-EU aims to provide in-depth analyses, strategies, and recommendations via the publication of **6 white papers** with the common conceptual model for BIOFIN-EU and relevant standards to ensure greater clarity and precision of what the concept entails and what is required for it to be deployed successfully, as well as **6 discussion papers** with contributions from research organisations, industry and standardisation bodies. For the first reporting period of the project, neither white nor discussion papers are anticipated.

3.2.2.3. Best Practice Publications

BIOFIN-EU will produce **6 best practice publications**, in the form of summaries for practitioners, dedicated to BIOFIN-EU's activities and outcomes such as the 10 Learning Sites, Accounting Standards, Business Models and others. The goal is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/recommendation/ practice regarding the deployment of the NbS Dashboard that will help actors navigate large-scale financing challenges and to develop, replicate, scale out and strengthen NbS-investment. BIOFIN-EU partners target to produce **1** best practice publication by M18.

3.2.2.4. Sectoral data and prediction reports

BIOFIN-EU will produce **6 sectoral data & prediction reports** that will provide data-driven insights and predictions about relevant innovations and research derived from project activities and the 10 Learning Sites. Adjusting to the project's needs, 2 Learning Sites were added, and one was updated leading to the increase of the LSs number from 8 to 10. No sectoral data and prediction reports are planned for the first reporting period of the project (M1-M18).

3.2.3. Ecosystem Building

BIOFIN-EU recognizes ecosystem building as essential in order to create impact. The BIOFIN-EU consortium partners aim to build a collaborative ecosystem by promoting multi-actor procedures, to bring together, learn each other's stories and experiences and ultimately empower key organisations to share information seamlessly with one another and work together.

To achieve this, BIOFIN-EU has primarily set up and will collaborate with an **external Advisory board**, with 8 members from the research, ecology insurance and agri-food industry domains, that will provide comments and advice about NbS/SFT domain-related, human-related and political-related issues in the context of the ongoing project.

Furthermore, the BIOFIN-EU consortium will enhance its ecosystem-building activities and therefore come closer to the fields of nature-based solutions and mainstream finance. During the project's lifetime, partners will participate with BIOFIN-EU booths in relevant commercial and trade events, organise scientific and industry-oriented events (webinars, workshops etc.), participate in conferences and organise dedicated sessions in relevant events and initiatives (e.g. BECC, IPCC).

Ecosystems involve diverse voices—more expertise and perspectives. By tapping into this collective wisdom, tangible, effective solutions emerge. Rather than isolating discussions within one department, ecosystems foster collaboration, leading to better outcomes. This will be done by a series of ecosystem activities that will include: **3 booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows; 6 participations in conferences; 6 joint events with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives; 2 advisory board meetings; 4 scientific/data science workshops and/or webinars; 10 industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars; and 10 open days for academic and commercial awareness.**

3.2.3.1. Booths at industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows

The BIOFIN-EU consortium has not yet participated in any industry fairs, exhibitions and trade shows due to the early stage of the project (M12). Participation in 1 relevant commercial and trade event is anticipated for the first reporting period of the project (M1-M18).

3.2.3.2. Participations in conferences

According to the plan, the BIOFIN-EU consortium will participate in 1 conference during the 1st reporting period and in 5 during the second reporting period. All future participations will also be included in Table 7 in the next iteration of the deliverable (M24). Up to the date of this deliverable, BIOFIN-EU partners participated in 2 conferences.

Table 7: BIOFIN-EU participation in conferences

Participation in conferences							
#	Date	Conference			Place	Partner	Target audience
1	01/10/2024	Sustainability conference	Europe	2024	London, UK	UL	Industry, Business partners; Investors; Others
2	15/10/2024	Future of Finance Summit 2024			Dublin, Ireland	UL	Industry, Business partners; Others

On October 1, 2024, our coordinator (**UL**) participated as a speaker at the [Sustainability Europe 2024 conference](#) on the Investment Stage organised by Reuters Events in London. With more than 750 sustainability executives and investors, *Sustainable Europe* is Europe's leading sustainability event bringing

together business and finance. During the event, John Garvey (UL) had the opportunity to discuss about BIOFIN-EU project with Dr Carmen Nuzzo, Executive Director, Transition Pathway Initiative Centre, LSE, Mark Campanale, Founder, Carbon Tracker Initiative and Anna Varpula, Director of Responsible Investment, Elo Mutual Pension Insurance Company (Figure 11), gain trusted insights and make meaningful connections with industry leaders. The panel also explored 'What data investors find investment-decision useful?' and 'Where they should source reliable information from?'. Questions around whether regulation has failed in its original intentions and if it had become a tick box exercise were also discussed. Around 30 stakeholders attended UL's session, coming from Asset Managers, Regulators, Financial Intermediaries and Advisory Services industries.

Figure 11: UL participating as a speaker in the Sustainability Europe 2024 conference.

On October 15, 2024, John Garvey from UL, participated as a speaker at [Future of Finance Summit 2024](#) in Dublin. UL highlighted the importance of understanding the way and the scale in which biodiversity loss risk is transmitted to the financial system, the existing data gaps and the complex link between nature and socio-economic systems which make risk assessments challenging. John Garvey (UL) also discussed the **Delphi Study on Data Bottlenecks in Banking Operations**, as part of the BIOFIN-EU project, aiming to bridge this gap, helping integrate biodiversity protection and restoration into mainstream finance (Figure 12). Over 300 financial services leaders attended the in-person event. IOB, seizing the opportunity of the event, created a video for the project with John Garvey (UL) presenting, including an interview of him discussing the challenges our project aims to address (see section 4.2.5.1 for more info).

Figure 12: UL presenting at Future of Finance Summit 2024

3.2.3.3. Joint events with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives

By M18, 2 joint events are anticipated and another 4 by the end of the project’s lifetime. Up to this deliverable date (M12) no synergies with relevant EU-projects and initiatives have been reported.

3.2.3.4. Advisory board meetings

By M18, 1 advisory board meeting is anticipated to provide comments and advice about NbS/SFT domain-related, human-related and political-related issues in the context of the ongoing project. One more meeting should take place during the second reporting period (M19-M36).

3.2.3.5. Scientific/data science workshops and/or webinars

The BIOFIN-EU consortium will participate in 1 scientific/data science workshop and/or webinar during the 1st reporting period and in 3 during the second reporting period. All future workshops/webinars will also be included in Table 8 in the next iteration of the deliverable (M24).

Table 8: BIOFIN-EU participation in scientific/data science workshops and/or webinars

Participation in scientific/data science workshops and/or webinars					
#	Date	Workshop/webinar	Place	Partner	Target audience
1	04/10/2024	Biodiversity Market: Challenges and Opportunities in Portugal	Lisbon, Portugal	COFAC	Research communities, Others

On October 4th, **COFAC** participated in the seminar "*Biodiversity Market: Challenges and Opportunities in Portugal*" which was held in a hybrid format, at Universidade Lusófona. The event featured speeches by Carla Pinto Cruz, Associate Professor at the University of Évora, and Carla Janeiro from University of Lisbon, who shared their views and experiences in an environment conducive to debate and collaboration. The

objective of this event was to promote discussion about the challenges and opportunities related to the biodiversity market in Portugal, addressing crucial topics for sustainable development and explore links with BIOFIN-EU. For the purposes of this event, an extra **customised poster** was designed by RAINNO and printed by COFAC as shown in Figure 13 below with information related to the BIOFIN-EU project. More than 30 people attended the event coming from National authorities, research community, international organisations (UN body, OECD etc) and other backgrounds.

Figure 13: COFAC discussing BIOFIN-EU project during the Biodiversity Market: Challenges and Opportunities in Portugal seminar

3.2.3.6. Industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars

During the first reporting period (M18) 4 industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars are anticipated. Up to M12, 4 workshops and webinars have been implemented in the BIOFIN-EU project. In the following table, main information regarding all events is being presented (Table 9).

Table 9: Timetable of the BIOFIN-EU industry-oriented workshops/webinars

Participation in industry-oriented workshops and/or webinars					
#	Date	Workshop/webinar	Place	Partner	Target audience
1	17/06/2024	Nature-positive investment strategies: Decision support for food companies	Online	ILSI	Industry, Business partners
2	27/06/2024	Banking Taskforce Workshop	Dublin, Ireland	UL	Industry, Business partners
3	18/09/2024	IOB webinar: "What is biodiversity finance?"	Online	ETI	Industry, Business partners; Other
4	25/09/2024	NetworkNature Annual Event 2024 Busting myths: People with nature	Brussels, Belgium	UL	Industry, Business partners; Local authorities; National/Regional

				authorities; Innovators; Investors; Research communities; Specific End-User Communities; Citizens; Other
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ILSI organised an online webinar entitled: “Nature-positive investment strategies: Decision support for food companies” on June 17, 2024, tailored for sustainability professionals in the agri-food industry. The webinar was focused on advancing tools and instruments that support nature-positive investments and explored actionable strategies for integrating biodiversity into investment decisions. Emilie Weynants from ILSI Europe, made the introduction and gave an overview of the BIOFIN-EU project (Figure 14) while Colas Chervier from UL, presented Nature-based solutions (NbS) and their role in food systems. Next, was our coordinator John Garvey from UL, who presented a Case Study of NbS-financing in the dairy sector and gave examples of collaborative research topics (Figure 15). In total, 18 participants attended the event from the industry and business sector.

Figure 14: Print Screens from the presentation of ILSI during the *Nature-positive investment strategies: Decision support for food companies* event and promo social media post

Figure 15: Print Screens from the presentation of UL in during the *Nature-positive investment strategies: Decision support for food companies event*

A Banking Taskforce Workshop was organised by **UL** and **IOB** at the IOB’s headquarters in Dublin on June 27, 2024. This industry-oriented workshop comprised 8 banking industry professionals with experience in green lending. The objective of the workshop was to (i) introduce the BIOFIN-EU project and its objectives to the banking sector, and (ii) better understand the green lending approaches used by banks, focusing on how to address poor or non-existing information in the lending process.

ETI, **NAT** and **UL** participated in the online webinar entitled [“What is biodiversity finance?”](#), hosted by **IOB** on September 18, 2024. During the event, our partners explored the concept of biodiversity, its impact on the financial sector, and potential interventions, such as Nature-based Solutions (Nbs), for the restoration and promotion of biodiversity. The event provided an opportunity to discuss crucial topics such as the meaning of biodiversity and why its protection is essential, interventions that can restore and promote biodiversity, while generating additional benefits (e.g. Nbs), how biodiversity loss affects the financial system and the importance for financial institutions to integrate nature-related risk assessments into their operations (Figure 16). The event attended more than 550 financial services professionals working across industry in banks, credit unions and other payment services firms.

Figure 16: Print Screens from ETI, NAT and UL while participating in the “What is biodiversity finance?” webinar and post on social media

Our coordinator, **UL**, participated in the [NetworkNature Annual Event 2024 | Busting myths: People with nature](#) on September 25, 2024 in Brussels. NetworkNature is a resource for the Nature-based Solutions (NbS) community, creating opportunities for local, regional and international cooperation to maximise the impact and spread of Nature-based Solutions. This event revolves around myths that practice, research, policy making, and business are busting or that need to be busted to bring about transformative change and reverse biodiversity loss. **UL** busted the myth that *It’s all about immediate profit*, by presenting the challenging goals of the BIOFIN-EU project (Figure 17). More than 100 people attended this session representing policymakers, local authorities, researchers, innovators, land planners and managers, investors and businesses, educators, artists, and society.

Figure 17: UL presenting BIOFIN-EU at NetworkNature annual event

On November 27, 2024, our partner **NAT**, participated at the [Sustainable Finance Week Ireland 2024](#). During this online webinar, NAT, had the opportunity to share with financial services professionals working across industry in banks, credit unions and other payment services firms the challenges in measuring Biodiversity.

3.2.3.7. Open days for academic and commercial awareness

Open days will be organized in academic settings, such as EU Business Schools, to disseminate research findings from the BIOFIN-EU project. These events are aimed at engaging undergraduate and postgraduate students, business school faculty members, and alumni. According to the initial Dissemination and Communication (DEC) plan (D7.1, M3), three open days were scheduled for the first reporting period and seven for the second reporting period. However, due to the project's early stage and limited research outputs thus far, the full set of 10 open days has been transferred to the later stages of the BIOFIN-EU project, after M18.

3.2.4. Capacity Building

Capacity building is crucial for the success of a project as it enhances the skills and knowledge of individuals and organisations involved. This leads to improved performance, adaptability to change, and a culture of innovation. It increases confidence and motivation, fostering sustainability by ensuring that teams can support and maintain project outcomes over the long term. It also facilitates better stakeholder engagement, risk mitigation, and optimal resource use. Additionally, knowledge transfer within partners and stakeholders is promoted, reducing the risk of dependency on a few individuals and contributing to overall project resilience and success.

Capacity building also enables individuals to enhance their skills and knowledge. This personal growth can lead to better overall personal and professional development. BIOFIN-EU will build capacity in skills development for current professional bankers and investment managers as well as the next generation of

business leaders in European business schools. This will be achieved through **20 co-creation Workshops in 6 different countries, 15 online training tutorials and 8 webinars.**

3.2.4.1. Co-creation workshops in 6 different countries

By M18, 8 co-creation workshops are anticipated and another 12 by the end of the project's lifetime. Workshops should take place in 6 different countries. Up to the date of this deliverable (M12), no workshop took place.

3.2.4.2. Online training tutorials

By M18, 3 online training tutorials are anticipated and another 12 until the end of the project. Up to the date of this deliverable (M12), no training tutorials took place.

3.2.4.3. Capacity building webinars

By M18, 3 capacity building webinars are anticipated and another 5 until the end of the project. Up to the date of this deliverable (M12), no capacity building webinars took place.

3.2.5. Standards & Policy Contribution

BIOFIN-EU will strive to influence ecology and ecosystem standard settings in order to create the enabling conditions for large-scale private finance and explore requirements and pathways for new accounting standards relating to proactive biodiversity investment (e.g. via IASB) The project partners will also try to push acquired knowledge into production environments and define future financial directions. For this aim the partners will produce **3 reports from the BIOFIN-EU Policy and Implementation Forum**, and **3 recommendations on accounting standards development** during the second reporting period of the project (M19-M36).

3.3. EC tools

BIOFIN-EU will take advantage of several of the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project's results. Up to the date of this deliverable (M12), none of these tools have been used due to the project's early stage and limited research outputs.

Figure 18: EC Tools available to support BIOFIN-EU's CED strategy

4. Communication Activities

4.1. Communication KPIs

BIOFIN-EU aims to raise public awareness of the project through a range of strategically planned actions that are accessible to internal and external stakeholders, the media and the general public and will:

- **Communicate impacts and benefits** of the project and its results for the duration of the project and after, by integrating various activities, tools and channels.
- **Customise communication activities** for different target groups as well as subgroups within.

BIOFIN-Eu's communication plan is a crucial component for:

- Raising awareness regarding the potential contribution of its nature-based solutions to the empowerment of the finance industry towards biodiversity protection and restoration investments,
- democratising knowledge, and
- attracting target groups and the general audience to solutions addressing urgent social and environmental challenges.

All partners share the responsibility of communicating the project and disseminating the results. Depending on each partner's expertise, experience, and resource allocation, KPIs and targets were allocated (Table 10).

D7.2: Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan

Table 10: Communication KPIs per partner

#	Communication KPIs	Target	1- UL	2- NAT	3- UGOT	4- UM	5- RAIN	6- SERDA	7- UNIPD	8- ETI	9- IOB	10- SUL	11- ILSI	12- QUB	13- COFAC
C.1	Branding & material														
C.1.1	Visual identity	1					1								
C.1.2	Logo	1					1								
C.1.3	Design of banners (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9					9								
C.1.4	Design of brochures (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9					9								
C.1.5	Printing and distribution of promotional materials - brochures	7000	2000	300	600	600	600	300	300	300	350	850	550	250	
C.2	Website														
C.2.1	website	1					1								
C.2.2	Unique visitors	5000					5000								
C.2.3	Blog posts	50					50								
C.3	Social Platforms														
C.3.1	Social media channels (Linkedin, Youtube, Facebook, Twitter, Slideshare)	5					5								
C.3.2	Social Media Audience	2000					2000								
C.3.3	Posts	200					200								
C.3.4	Monthly impressions	400					400								
C.3.5	hashtags to use in social media	5					5								
C.3.6	share of highly relevant articles/ per month >2	72					72								
C.4	e-Newsletters														
C.4.1	e-newsletters	15					15								
C.4.2	subscriptions	1000					1000								
C.4.3	interactions	800					800								
C.4.4	highly relevant articles/ per e-newsletter	10					10								
C.5	Multimedia														
C.5.1	Published videos (>1 for each pilot and >2 for the project)	10	1				2	1	1	2					3
C.5.2	Podcast series (10 episodes each) in Google or Spotify podcasts app	2					2								
C.6	Multiplier campaigns														
C.6.1	Press releases	8					8								
C.6.2	Published articles in online platforms and offline media	10					10								

Communication KPIs have been distributed between **two reporting periods** (M1-M18, M19-M36) in which the DEC plan will be updated in 4 versions. This is the **second version**, updated with the achieved communication KPIs up to **M12** as shown in Table 11.

Table 11: Communication KPIs per reporting period and M12 status

#	Communication KPIs	Target	Reporting Phases		
			M1-M18	M19-M36	M12 status
C.1	Branding & material				
C.1.1	Visual identity	1	1	-	1/1
C.1.2	Logo	1	1	-	1/1
C.1.3	Design of banners (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9	9	-	1/9
C.1.4	Design of brochures (>1 per LS and >1 for the project)	9	9	-	1/9
C.1.5	Printing and distribution of promotional materials - brochures	7000	2000	5000	175/2000
C.2	Website				
C.2.1	website	1	1	-	1/1
C.2.2	Unique visitors	5000	2000	3000	6200/2000
C.2.3	Blog posts	50	25	25	8/25
C.3	Social Platforms				
C.3.1	Social media channels (Linkedin, Youtube, Facebook, Twitter, Slideshare)	5	5	-	5/5
C.3.2	Social Media Audience	2000	700	1300	457/700
C.3.3	Posts	200	100	100	149/100
C.3.4	Monthly impressions	400	400	400	1770/400
C.3.5	hashtags to use in social media	5	5	-	5/5
C.3.6	share of highly relevant articles/ per month >2	72	36	36	16/36
C.4	e-Newsletters				
C.4.1	e-newsletters	15	7	8	3/7
C.4.2	subscriptions	1000	400	600	167/400
C.4.3	interactions	800	300	500	573/300
C.4.4	highly relevant articles/ per e-newsletter (total)	10 (150)	10 (70)	10 (80)	30/70
C.5	Multimedia				
C.5.1	Published videos (>1 for each pilot and >2 for the project)	10	1	9	1/1
C.5.2	Podcast series (10 episodes each) in Google or Spotify podcasts app	2	-	2	-
C.6	Multiplier campaigns				
C.6.1	Press releases	8	3	5	1/3
C.6.2	Published articles in online platforms and offline media	10	4	6	0/4

4.2. Communication Measures and Tools

4.2.1. Branding & Material

4.2.1.1. Visual identity

BIOFIN-EU's communication material aims to promote and increase stakeholder and public awareness of the project. To multiply the sphere of influence, both digital and physical forms have been created. Offline communication products have the added advantage of being physical, tangible and occupy space to captivate audiences during the project's participation in events and conferences. These materials focus on a more visually engaging way of raising awareness about the project's aims, activities and results. It is advantageous to follow certain rules when utilising offline material – regardless of the implementation strategies; well-prepared headlines, wisely colours usage, focus on benefits – and keep the tone and the message aligned to the intended target audience.

Brand Book

To achieve this goal, all of the aforementioned are aligned with **BIOFIN-EU's brand book** (Figure 19), to ensure that the produced communication material aligns with the project's visual identity and the branding guidelines. The full version of the BIOFIN-EU brand book is presented in **Annex II**.

Figure 19: BIOFIN-EU Brand Book

4.2.1.2. Templates

Because BIOFIN-EU is being presented at numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, a **presentation (ppt) template** (Figure 20), as well as a **document (word) template** (Figure 21), have been designed in line with BIOFIN-EU's visual identity in order to maintain consistency, professionalism and promote its recognition. Additionally, more templates have been designed for several events purposes such as an event's **minute's template** and an **agenda template** (Figures 22 & 23).

Figure 20: BIOFIN-EU Presentation Template

Figure 21: BIOFIN-EU Word Template

Figure 22: BIOFIN-EU Minutes Template

Figure 23: BIOFIN-EU Agenda Template

BIOFIN-EUs **deliverable template** (Figure 24) is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and is used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project’s logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and title) as well as the writer’s information. For the full version of the deliverable template see **Annex III**.

BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

DX.X: [Deliverable Title]

Lead Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner)]

Funded by the European Union

BIOFIN EU

DX.X: Deliverable Title

Grant Agreement No.	101135476
Project Acronym	BIOFIN-EU
Project Title	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2023-BIODIV-01-9
Start – ending date	1 January 2024 – 31 December 2026
Project Website	biofin-project.eu
Work Package	WPx: Title of the WP
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)
Relevant Task(s)	Tx.x Title of the Task
Deliverable type Dissemination level	R – Report; DEC: Websites, press & media actions, videos, etc; OTHER: Software, etc. PU: Public; SEN: Sensitive; CI: Classified
Due Date of Deliverable	DD Month 20YY
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Figure 24: BIOFIN-EU Deliverable Template

EU Emblem

All BIOFIN-EU dissemination and communication material acknowledge the requirements set out by the European Commission and include the EU flag and the source of funding, based on Article 17.2 “Visibility-European flag and funding statement” of the Grant Agreement (Figure 25).

Figure 25: EU Emblem

Disclaimer for publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

The disclaimer and acknowledgement of EU funding should be on the cover or the first pages following the editor’s mention.

All **research publications** should include an acknowledgement of Horizon EU funding and the following disclaimer:

"Funding for this research has been provided by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme BIOFIN-EU (Grant Agreement Number 101135476). Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

4.2.1.3. Logo

The logo is the main tool to create a direct visual recognition of the BIOFIN-EU project. It was therefore, chosen to be simple, give a hint of a story, and be easily recognizable. The BIOFIN-EU logo showcases the acronym using a clear and modern font. The BIOFIN-EU's logo is composed of two parts (Figure 26). At the top, a graph chart arrow going up with leaves growing on it, representing ecological and sustainable growth. Below the arrow, BIOFIN-EU's acronym is presented using three different colours. The logo is used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness, throughout the project's lifetime and beyond. The main version of the logo used for most of the communication and dissemination material is shown in Figure 26 below:

Figure 26: BIOFIN-EU Logo

4.2.1.4. Roll-up Banner

BIOFIN-EU's roll-up banners should be used to promote the project, and the learning sites at physical events for eye-catching identification of the BIOFIN-EU booth. The first banner of the project has already been designed (Figure 27), while the other **eight** (one for each learning site) are planned. The total number of banners might be adjusted to the project's needs, as by the current month (M12) 2 Learning Sites were added, and one was updated leading to the increase of the LSs number from 8 to 10. The general project's banner includes the most important information related to the BIOFIN-EU, the motto of the project "***Flip the script: Unlock finance to protect and restore biodiversity***", the social media accounts, as well as a QR code, which leads to the project website providing direct access to the project's scope and activities.

Figure 27: BIOFIN-EU Banner

4.2.1.5. Brochures

Brochures are designed for online distribution and at physical events. The first brochure presenting the project mission, methodology, consortium and expected results is already designed (Figure 28). The other **eight** brochures will be dedicated to the learning sites. The total number of the brochures might be adjusted to the project’s needs, as by the current month (M12) 2 Learning Sites were added, and one was updated leading to the increase of the LSs number from 8 to 10.

Figure 28: BIOFIN-EU Brochure

Up to this point **175** brochures have been distributed in different events (Figure 29) that the BIOFIN-EU partners participated in. For example, **ETI** shared brochures during the [Network Nature Conference](#) in Brussels in September 2024.

Figure 29: ETI shared BIOFIN-EU brochures during the *NetworkNature* conference

Furthermore, ILSI shared brochures during the [Food Integrity Global \(FIG\) 2024](#) event in Amsterdam in September 2024, at the [22nd World Congress of Food Science and Technology \(IUFoST 2024\)](#) event in Rimini in September 2024, during the [WUR Career Day](#) in Wageningen University in October 2024 and at ILSI Europe [Annual Symposium and Early Career Scientist Event](#) in Denmark, in November 2024 (Figure 30).

Figure 30: ILSI distributing brochures during the Annual Symposium and Early Career Scientist Event (top left), *IUFoST 2024* (top right), *WUR Career Day* (bottom left), and *FIG 2024* (bottom right) events

COFAC had the opportunity to distribute the project's brochure to enhance stakeholders engagement and raise awareness about our project, its aims, activities and results during the seminar [Biodiversity Market: Challenges and Opportunities](#) in Portugal, in October 2024 (Figure 31).

Figure 31: COFAC distributing brochures during the *Biodiversity Market: Challenges and Opportunities in Portugal* seminar

4.2.1.6. Other

Other communication materials that could be used to attract a wider audience include folders, notebooks, pens, magnets, and bags. Examples of potential communication material can be found in **Annex II** as part of the Brand book. All material must be in line with the project's visual identity (use of defined colour palettes and styles).

4.2.2. Website

BIOFIN-EU's website (www.biofin-project.eu) has already been developed. The project's website is the primary communication and dissemination platform to enable target groups and BIOFIN-EU's stakeholders to access project development and results, and to grasp and assess the added value and the impact of nature-positive financial decision support. The website will be updated frequently and will utilise input from all partners. It provides an overview of the learning sites, partners and links to their websites and it will host all the public dissemination deliverables, promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, workshops, press releases, printed material, publications etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. It will also host digital visualisations of project processes and results, to make them accessible to a wider audience. In addition, the website is mobile-friendly, increasing accessibility and maximising the impact of the project (Figure 32).

Figure 32: BIOFIN-EU Website on mobile and desktop

BIOFIN-EU's website has a twofold role as it serves as the principal reference point for the project, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, and documents for download and enabling access to social media accounts of BIOFIN-EU. Furthermore, it acts as a resource centre for research on topics related to NbS, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in M3, the BIOFIN-EU website is hosted at <https://biofin-project.eu/> and contains the following sections and features:

1. **Home/Landing page:** Includes the project logo, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, SlideShare), a button for sign-up in the BIOFIN-EU's newsletter, BIOFIN-EU's Objectives and expected results, all partners logos, EU's Emblem with the disclaimer. The main contact information for the coordinator and communication manager is provided at the bottom as well as the cookies and privacy policy.
2. **About:**
 - Objectives,
 - NbS Dashboard,
 - Partners
3. **Learning Sites:** Includes descriptions of the Learning Sites. Two more Learning Sites were added according to the project's needs, and one was updated. Up to date, the number of Learning Sites on the project's website have increased from 8 to 10.
4. **News & Events:**

- Blog (Press releases and blog posts are the main content and inform stakeholders of all project's activities)
- Events (All the events that BIOFIN-EU partners organise or participate in)

5. Resources:

- Deliverables
- Newsletters
- Publication
- Press Kit
- Videos and Podcasts – These 2 subcategories will be created as soon as the materials are ready.

Within the “Publication” submenu we created a new subcategory named “Initial User Requirements” after the completion of **Milestone 3** of our project. When this option is selected, you are redirected to the page dedicated to the Requirements Road map, a document created by our partner, University of Gothenburg.

6. Synergies: Presentation of relevant projects and initiatives that BIOFIN-EU collaborates with.
7. Contact: All contact information for the BIOFIN-EU project is available under this section enabling the easiest communication with our stakeholders through email and a contact form for messages. In addition, the visitor can find links to all the social media accounts of the projects.
8. Subscribe Button: A dedicated button that redirects visitors to the subscription page for the BIOFIN-EU newsletter.
9. Cookies & Privacy Policy: The Cookies Policy, together with the Privacy Policy has also been included in the BIOFIN-EU website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

To ensure the proper visibility of the website and monitor the relevant KPIs, the platform “Google Analytics” is used, which is a well-established web analytics tool provided by Google and tracks website traffic. Although Google Analytics provides a wide range of metrics to track, we focus on the website's unique visitors, i.e. new users (Figure 33).

Figure 33: BIOFIN-EU Website Metrics Overview

On M12⁴, the current status of the KPI about the unique visitors of the website totals to **6200** users, out of 5.000 target for the end of the project.

Another website KPI, as indicated in the Grant Agreement, is the number of the **published blog posts** (Figure 34) on the website. The purpose of the blog posts is to provide insightful content to the users, keeping them updated with all the BIOFIN-EU news and events by offering extra information and details, compared to the social media posts. The KPI goal is to publish **50** posts by the end of the project, while the current number of published posts is **8**. All the blog posts are published by RAIN, while the content contextually comes from the partners.

Figure 34: Blog posts on BIOFIN-EU official website

4.2.3. Social Media Platforms

To apply the multi-actor approach and establish a two-way communication with the audience, BIOFIN-EU aims to have a strong social media presence. **Five media channels** (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, X (former Twitter), and SlideShare) were selected based on the following factors:

⁴ The latest update of all the website’s KPI numbers took place on 16/12/24.

- The most cost-effective set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholder groups;
- The most adequate, valid and powerful media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and several key stakeholders;
- The most popular social media platforms used by BIOFIN-EU's partners, to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

Since the M1 of the project, BIOFIN-EU has been active on social media platforms (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare) targeting to reach a diverse audience and connect with potential stakeholders who may prefer one platform over another. Each social media channel is individually presented in upcoming sections.

When it comes to content creation, there are several parameters to consider for BIOFIN-EU's social media:

- **Consistency** is the main pillar of our social media strategy, maintaining a consistent brand identity by using consistent colours, tones and messaging to make BIOFIN-EU easily recognizable. Also, in terms of frequency, a constant and active appearance on social media boosts the project's visibility and attracts new followers;
- **Authenticity** is crucial in BIOFIN-EU social media profiles. That's why we share genuine content that reflects the BIOFIN-EU project;
- **Eye-catching posts** lead to higher conversions with the prioritisation of high-quality images, videos, and graphics that are visually appealing and consistent with the BIOFIN-EU brand. All the material is designed in a way that can be easily understood even without sound on (especially referring to videos);
- **Content** that is value-driven and characterised by **variety**. The BIOFIN-EU posts can be in the form of informative content, entertainment, or inspiration. This makes it more likely for people to engage with the content and share it;
- **Call to Action (CTA)**. Encouraging our audience to take action, whether it's liking, sharing, commenting or visiting the BIOFIN-EU website, can drive engagement.

The aforementioned are summed up and visually presented in the figure below (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Content of the BIOFIN-EU's social media posts

To maximise the project’s visibility and impact, BIOFIN-EU exploits the consortium’s already-developed social media networks. Consortium’s partners are expected to share, publish and retweet content from the BIOFIN-EU social media accounts and BIOFIN-EU website, thus, increasing traction for project-related work and increasing traffic on partner’s websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content for the project’s actions and share it through their channels. Social media accounts were collected from all partners at the beginning of the project, to enhance BIOFIN-EU’s online visibility by creating a social network and promoting BIOFIN-EU’s activities and results.

In order to monitor the social media accounts and ensure their effectiveness, a number of metrics have been tracked, in line with the KPIs targets claimed in the Grant Agreement. Measuring our social media audience provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of our social media strategy and the visibility of the project. The KPI target that needs to be reached by the end of the project is to have a total audience of 2.000 social media followers for all the platforms. The current audience is **457** (M12) (Figure 37). Although this number seems low compared to our target, it is reasonable as the social media engagement in the first year of similar projects is limited.

The monthly total impression is another KPI we track, in line with the Grant Agreement. For LinkedIn and Facebook, we consider the metrics “Members reached” and “Reach”, respectively, which represent the number of users who saw BIOFIN-EU content, i.e. how many different people it reaches. This metric is called “Unique Impressions” or “Reach”. For X and SlideShare, this specific metric is not provided. Instead, we track the total impressions, meaning the number of times the BIOFIN-EU content is seen, including multiple views from individual users. The monthly target for impressions, on average for all the months of the project, should be 400. Currently, the average for the first 12 months of BIOFIN-EU is 1770 (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Graph of the social media impressions per month

Another KPI refers to the **number of posts**, both the original content uploaded by the BIOFIN-EU accounts and the repost of the relevant-to-the-project posts coming from the partners’ accounts. The total goal for this KPI is 200, and currently, we have posted **149** posts, showcasing the constant online presence of BIOFIN-EU. Finally, highly relevant articles will be shared monthly on the project’s social media to enhance the engagement with the audience. The total number of articles that should be shared by the end of the project is **72**, and up to date (M12) we have shared **16** reports and articles.

Figure 37: BIOFIN-EU’s social media metrics

4.2.3.1. LinkedIn

A [LinkedIn profile](#) was created to network with BIOFIN-EU target audiences and promote the project’s activities. As such, all project news is published on LinkedIn profile and partners have the opportunity to start conversations on particular themes and attract a wider audience. Figures 38 and 39 provide an overview of BIOFIN-EU’s LinkedIn profile.

Figure 38: BIOFIN-EU LinkedIn page

Figure 39: Sample posts of the BIOFIN-EU LinkedIn page

4.2.3.2. Facebook

BIOFIN-EU’s [Facebook page](#) was developed to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level (Figure 40). Sample posts of the BIOFIN-EU Facebook page are shown in Figure 41.

Figure 40: BIOFIN-EU Facebook page

Figure 41: Sample posts of the BIOFIN-EU Facebook page

4.2.3.3. X (Twitter)

An [X \(Twitter\) account](#) was created to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policymakers and advisors. BIOFIN-EU will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact and post news, events and updates on the project’s status (Figure 42 and 43).

X's popularity and concise, simple format make it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our target audiences and their respective communities. Twitter will also be used to connect with “influencers” in the research and business topics of the BIOFIN-EU project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 42: BIOFIN-EU X profile

Figure 43: Sample posts of the BIOFIN-EU X profile

4.2.3.4. YouTube

A [YouTube channel](#) is used in order to host and promote BIOFIN-EU’s videos, which are of wide variety, such as interviews, case studies, demos etc. BIOFIN-EU’s YouTube channel is mainly used for awareness and training purposes, focusing on all BIOFIN-EU’s target groups and every stakeholder interested in biodiversity, finance and nature-positive investments (Figure 44).

Figure 44: BIOFIN-EU YouTube channel and videos

4.2.3.5. SlideShare

A [SlideShare account](#) has been created to present project material in an engaging visual format that appeals to BIOFIN-EU's audience. Project presentations are available for any interested stakeholder providing key information on the project implementation and activities (Figure 45).

Figure 45: BIOFIN-EU SlideShare account

4.2.3.6. Hashtags

Creating hashtags relevant to the project and its outcomes help reach target audiences and make it easy to find BIOFIN-EU generated knowledge. Hashtags divide the project's main topics into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases and help increase visibility in the social media environment, while they make BIOFIN-EU's messages stand out and influence relevant communities. Further tracking of the hashtags facilitates the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data. The project has set five official distinctive hashtags (in line with the Communication KPIs of the Grant Agreement), which are **#biodiversity**, **#nature**, **#greenfinance**, **#sustainablefinance**, **#sustainability** (Figure 46). These hashtags have been chosen by the consortium as the most relevant among a list of 9 hashtags, during the Kick-off meeting, in Brussels (Belgium) on 8-9 February 2024. Additionally, two more hashtags are always considered: **#HorizonEU** and **#ResearchImpactEU**. Finally, other hashtags could be occasionally used, considering the respective content of the posts each time.

Figure 46: BIOFIN-EU hashtags

4.2.4. e-Newsletters

An online newsletter is published every 4 months (starting M04) to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This includes the latest developments, activities, and where to find recent reports and publications. Also, there will be additional newsletter issues as “special editions”, and announcements for upcoming events, workshops and demonstrations.

Subscriptions can take place at events as well as in BIOFIN-EU’s website (Figure 47). Upon Newsletter registration, BIOFIN-EU pays special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the user’s personal data. Newsletter recipients are asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data are fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework, and the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties are able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the BIOFIN-EU Newsletters and all collected data are stored and saved in the responsible partner’s servers. Users’ data are inaccessible to third parties. A more detailed description of data collection, storage and handling is presented in the respective deliverables (D1.2 – Data Management Plan M6, D1.3 – Data Management Plan Update M18, D1.4 – Data Management Plan Final M36). A professional marketing platform (i.e., Mailchimp) is used to automate the distribution among contact points. Furthermore, to achieve broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, BIOFIN-EU partners are encouraged to promote newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

Subscribe to our newsletter.

Your email address

I have read and agree to the terms & conditions

Sign up

Figure 47: Subscription form on the website

The first issue of the newsletter was released in April 2024 (M04), followed by the second issue in August 2024 (M08), as planned (Figure 48). Additionally, in November 2024, we launched a special issue titled 'What is Biodiversity Finance?', dedicated to the IOB webinar (see section 3.2.3.6). This special issue included details about the topics discussed during the webinar and provided links to BIOFIN-EU blog posts for further reading. All newsletters, drafted and designed by RAINNO, and approved by the coordinator, with some of the content provided by the partners. All the issues of the newsletter mentioned above are distributed to the subscribers and uploaded on the project's website. In parallel, the issues will be promoted on the project's social media pages, via "call to action" and informative posts, before and after their release, respectively. There is a specific plan for the distribution of the BIOFIN-EU newsletter, in terms of release frequency and number of issues (Figure 48). The "Special Edition" issues, as well as, the event announcements will be launched based on the project's progress and results, thus it is not possible to plan them beforehand.

36-MONTH NEWSLETTER PLANNING & STATUS

EXTRA SPECIAL EDITION ISSUES & UPCOMING EVENT ANNOUNCEMENTS:

- SPECIAL ISSUE "WHAT IS BIODIVERSITY FINANCE?" | NOVEMBER 2024

Figure 48: Newsletter plan and status

In total at least **15 e-newsletters** will be published in the span of the project, which will also contain at least **10 highly relevant articles each**, anticipating **1.000 newsletter subscribers** and **800 interactions** over the course of the project. The structure of the newsletter is standardised; however, small changes can be made contextually:

- Introduction of the project
- Project Update / Key news and project events
- Dedicated section to a partner (when applicable)
- Resources for further reading (suggested by all partners)

The newsletter is open even for non-subscribers and all the issues can be found on the project's website in the [dedicated section](#). The upcoming 3rd BIOFIN-EU issue is currently under construction and is expected to be published by the end of December 2024 (M12).

When it comes to performance tracking, the relevant KPI target of the newsletter subscribers is 1.000 and the total interactions 800, as claimed in the Grant Agreement. As interactions, we consider all the newsletter opens and the clicks inside them. Currently, the subscribers total to **167** unique email addresses and the total number of interactions for the first two issues and the special issue is **573**. Each Newsletter includes a dedicated section with at least 10 relevant articles, to further engage subscribers who are interested in topics related to NbS, biodiversity, sustainable finance and more.

Figure 49: Newsletter issues No1, No2 and special edition

4.2.5. Multimedia

4.2.5.1. Published videos

Due to its flexibility, video can be a highly effective marketing tool that businesses can utilise to their advantage. By developing videos of the BIOFIN-EU project as well as evidence/results-based videos of the learning sites it is anticipated that interest and enquiries from BIOFIN-EU's target audiences will be generated. At least **10 videos** will be produced and published (1 for each learning site and 2 for the overall project). All videos will be uploaded on the BIOFIN-EU website and YouTube channel. By M18, 1 project video is anticipated and another 9 by the end of the project.

As mentioned in section 3.2.3.6, IOB created a dedicated video (Figure 50) for the project with John Garvey (UL) while presenting at Future of Finance Summit, including a short interview of him discussing the challenges our project aims to address. John Garvey pointed out that financial services professionals can make a difference to biodiversity, as this relates to the BIOFIN-EU project - establish a comprehensive framework and technology that fosters the necessary conditions for nature-positive investments.

Figure 50: Video on BIOFIN-EU website of John Garvey from his presentation at Future of Finance Summit in Dublin

4.2.5.2. Podcast series

Podcasts are digital audio files presented in a series, typically with new instalments received automatically by subscribers. This on-demand technology is growing in popularity with 464.7 million podcast listeners globally in 2023⁵. BIOFIN-EU will create **2 podcast series of ten episodes each**, to enrich and diversify the website and address auditory learning styles. Content created by partners will follow an overarching theme that will make for a cohesive, entertaining series. The length of each episode will be around 10-15 minutes. The podcast series will be developed during months 19-36 and will be organised by RAINNO.

Two podcast categories will be designed to focus on the following categories:

- Interviews of the consortium partners, project advancements and results, and future directions.
- Capacity building on sustainable finance and nature-positive investments.

4.2.6. Multiplier Campaigns

A multiplier campaign combines several communication and dissemination strategies that reinforce a message to obtain a greater positive impact. To this end, BIOFIN-EU broadens the scope of communication tools and channels to include press releases and articles published in online platforms and offline media. These additional channels add credibility and visibility and connect with local and regional networks.

4.2.6.1. Press Releases

During the lifetime of the project, press releases will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project, its latest activities and developments to a broader audience as well as addressing more specific stakeholders. To maximise influence on local stakeholders, the consortium is advised to translate all press releases into all consortium partners' languages (Figure 51). More specifically, the first press release was developed after BIOFIN-EU's kick-off meeting which took place at M2 and distributed to consortium members and various digital media, such as [Oppla](#) and [Network Nature](#) (Figure 52). The target is **8 press releases in total**. Until M18, 2 more press releases are anticipated and another 5 until the end of the project's lifetime.

⁵ <https://www.demandsage.com/podcast-statistics/#:~:text=There%20are%20464.7%20million%20podcast,podcast%20listeners%20in%20the%20world.>

Figure 51: The first BIOFIN-EU press release

Figure 52: The BIOFIN-EU press release on relevant platforms

ETI and ILSI shared details about the launch of the BIOFIN-EU project on their websites making a collaborative effort to increase awareness and project visibility. More specifically, [ETI added the project in its portfolio](#) by presenting the context and a description of BIOFIN-EU and ETI’s contribution to enrich the panel of learning cases (Figure 53).

Figure 53: BIOFIN-EU project presence in ETI's website

On the other hand, ILSI, announced [the launch of the BIOFIN-EU project](#) through its website, and added the project on its [portfolio](#) and in their [2025 activity document](#) which is distributed to all members.

Figure 54: BIOFIN-EU project presence in ILSI's website

4.2.6.2. Published articles on online platforms and offline media

During the lifetime of the project, consortium partners will leverage print (newspapers, magazines) and online media (such as blogs) related to the researched topics of the project, to maximise the project's impact and engage stakeholders outside the prioritised target groups. BIOFIN-EU will publish and

contribute at least **10 articles** on online platforms and offline media. Until M18, 4 articles are anticipated to be published in online platforms and offline media and another 5 until the end of the project's lifetime. Up to the date of this deliverable (M12), no articles were published yet.

5. Exploitation Activities

BIOFIN-EU will produce several Key Exploitable results (KERs) during the lifespan of the project. The preliminary results identified during the proposal stage (KERs), and potential pathways for their exploitation as well as the procedure for identifying new potential KERs (and IPs) during project implementation have been analysed in **version 1 of the DEC Plan deliverable in M3**.

All the measures to ensure sustainability and effective IPR management of BIOFIN-EU results have been developed by the **Toolset for Multiplying Impact (D7.5) at M12**, under Task 7.4 IPR Management and Sustainability Plan, which includes an IPR, a go-to-market strategy and a sustainability plan and will be updated as a second and third version at M24 and M36 respectively.

6. Conclusions

D7.1 “Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M3”, has provided an overview of the communication, dissemination and exploitation phases during the whole project lifetime. The intention of this document (D7.2 Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M12) is to elaborate further to the initial DEC plan which has been implemented during the first period of the BIOFIN-EU project, as well as the tools that have been utilised in order to reach DEC’s KPIs and project’s audience. The second function is to monitor the progress of the plan.

More specifically, the document covers a wide range of key activities (as well as sets their timelines) to be conducted to meet the dissemination, communication, and exploitation targets. All partners will be actively involved in the communication and dissemination of BIOFIN-EU aiming to ensure the proper exploitation of the project’s outcomes and maximise the impact.

The next iteration of the document (D7.3 Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan M24), will be an updated version of the DEC plan. It will evaluate the current plan to identify weaknesses and strengths of the applied activities and tools and establish objectives and concrete actions beyond M12 until the third iteration (M24). The third version (M24) will focus on the diffusion of the scientific and technological information generated during the project and emphasis will be placed on sparking interest in the BIOFIN-EU platform and broadening stakeholder engagement with the project activities and results.

Annex I: BIOFIN-EU Overview of the D&C reporting tool

Instructions

This spreadsheet is designed to report on dissemination and communication activities directly linked to the key performance indicators (KPIs) outlined in the Grant Agreement (e.g., it includes specific targets for each partner and reporting period).

- Sheet 1A provides the total KPI targets per reporting period and a short description of each KPI.
- Sheet 2A provides the total KPI targets per partner.
- Sheet 3A monitors the KPI status.
- Sheets 1 - 3A are dedicated to each partner, containing two tables:
 - Dissemination Activities (e.g., events, synergies, publications) & Communications Activities (e.g., social media, interviews):
 - Please use the drop down menu to select the "Month" of the activity (column A) and double click to add the "Activity Day" (column B)
 - Please use the drop down menu to select "KPI" (column C) including both Dissemination and Communication KPIs, then provide the "Title / Description", "Link", and "Annoting instance" (columns E, F, G).
 - If you are reporting Dissemination activities, please add "Type of stakeholders reached" and "No. of stakeholders reached" (columns H, I). Please indicate if the activity should be considered a "Joint activity" (external to the consortium), and "if yes, please indicate with whom" (columns J, K).
 - If you need to add more info, please use the "Notes" (column L)
 - In case there is nothing to report in a month, please make sure to select "Nothing to report" from the drop down menu in "KPI" (column C).
 - If you are reporting an activity beyond the Bio4Finance KPIs, please state "Other" in the "KPI" category in column C.
 - For Communication activities, there is no need to add "Type of stakeholders reached", "No. of stakeholders reached, Joint Action?", and "if yes, with whom?"
 - The "Report Status" (column D) gives you information on the status of the reporting process. Please don't overwrite, it is autofilled!
 - The "DVC" (column M) indicates if the activity reported in a dissemination or a communication activity. Please don't overwrite, it is autofilled!

Important notes

Please click on the link on "Proofing material uploaded (Photos, screenshots etc.)" (cell G1) to upload photos or other relevant material (e.g. agenda, presentations) from events that may be used for dissemination and communication purposes.

For enhanced visibility and credibility, it is highly recommended that all dissemination posts related to the project come from your organization's official social media account, rather than personal accounts. Additionally, please ensure to tag BIOFIN-EU in your posts to increase engagement.

Report Status (D) column:

- All info added
- Basic info missing
- Minor info missing
- Status (I) column:
- KPI achieved
- KPI on progress
- No progress has been done yet

Please ensure to include the exact date of the activity and any relevant information. Please focus on input/activities that relate directly to the KPIs.

Navigation Bar: Instructions | 1A - KPIs per RP | 2A - Partner breakdown | 3A - Monitoring | 1. UL | 2. NAT | 3. UG | 4. UM | 5. ...

Annex II: BIOFIN-EU Brand Book

BIOFIN-EU

Flip the script:
Unlock finance
to protect & restore
biodiversity

Brand Guidelines

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Project Logo |

BIOFIN-EU

Logo Variations |

BIOFIN-EU

Colour scheme - Palette |

Primary

#E68E10	WEB #A88F6F
#E68E10	WEB #F8D556
#E68E10	WEB #117887
#E68E10	WEB #C2C4C6

Secondary

#C3E591	PAINTONE 7504 C	#E68E10	WEB #E8A48C
#C3E591	PAINTONE 7737 C	#E68E10	WEB #578E87
#C3E591	PAINTONE 7733 C	#E68E10	WEB #78A4A4
#C3E591	PAINTONE 427 C	#E68E10	WEB #90808A
#C3E591		#C3E591	PAINTONE 7535 C
#C3E591		#C3E591	PAINTONE 5177 C
#C3E591		#C3E591	PAINTONE 5493 C
#C3E591		#C3E591	PAINTONE Cool Gray 7 C

BIOFIN-EU

Typography |

Aa Zwo Pro

Headline 1
Zwo Pro Extra Bold

Headline 2
Zwo Pro Bold

Body Text 1
Zwo Pro Regular

Body Text 2
Zwo Pro Light

BIOFIN-EU

Applications |

BIOFIN-EU

Annex III: BIOFIN-EU Deliverable Template

BIOFIN-EU

PROTECTING AND RESTORING BIODIVERSITY USING MAINSTREAM FINANCE

DX.X: [Deliverable Title]

Lead Author: [Author Name and Surname (Partner)]

Funded by the European Union

DX.X: Deliverable Title BIOFIN-EU

Grant Agreement No.	101135476
Project Acronym	BIOFIN-EU
Project Title	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Horizon Europe Call Topic	HORIZON-CA-2023-BIODIV-01-9
Start - ending date	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2026
Project Website	biofin-project.eu
Work Package	WPc: Title of the WP
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)
Deliverable Title(s)	Tc: Title of the Task
Deliverable type / Dissemination level	B - Report; CEC - Webinars, press & media actions, videos, etc; OTHER: Software, etc. EU: Public; SEN: Sensative; CI: Classified
Due Date of Deliverable	00 Month 20YY
Actual Submission Date	00 Month 20YY
Responsible Author	[Author Name and Surname (Partner)]
Contributors	[Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)]
Reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's Name and Surname (Partner)]

Document History

Date	Version	Changes	Contributor(s)
DD/MM/YYYY	VL1	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)
DD/MM/YYYY	VLX	[Description of changes]	Contributors' Name and Surname (Partner)

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DX.X: Deliverable Title BIOFIN-EU

BIOFIN-EU Consortium			
#	Organisation name	Short name	Country
1	UNIVERSITY OF LIMBURG	UL	BE
2	STICHTING NATURALIS BIODIVERSITY CENTER	NATURALIS	NL
3	SÖDERTÖRNES UNIVERSITET	SÖDIT	SE
4	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	UM	NL
5	ΒΑΙΝΝΟ (ΙΟΤΗ) ΚΕΦΑΛΑΙΟΥΧΗ ΕΤΑΙΡΕΙΑ	ΒΑΙΝΝΟ	EL
6	SARAJEVSKA REGIONALNA RAZVOJNA AGENCIJA SERDA ODO SARAJEVO	SERDA	BA
7	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA	UNIPD	IT
8	ETFOR SRL	ETFOR SRL	IT
9	THE INSTITUTE OF BANKERS IN IRELAND	IOB	IE
10	SUSTAINABILITY LITVAKI TEST	LITVAKI	FR
11	INTERNATIONAL LIFE SCIENCES INSTITUTE EUROPEAN BRANCH A/S&L	ILSI	BE
12	THE QUEEN'S UNIVERSITY OF BELFAST	QUB	UK
13	COFAC COOPERATIVA DE FORMAGAO E ANIMAGAO CULTURAL CHL	COFAC	PT

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